

SECTION OF EARTH SCIENCES

MODELLING THE PROCESS OF USING SPACECRAFT FOR THEIR INTENDED PURPOSE

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Abstract

The article discusses an approach to modelling the process of using spacecraft for various purposes, including Earth remote sensing (ERS) systems, satellite communications, radar and radio-electronic reconnaissance. The relevance of the work is due to the growing need for high-precision forecasting of the capabilities and effectiveness of spacecraft use in civil and military tasks of operational observation and information support. The aim of the study is to create a structured methodology for modelling spacecraft application scenarios using modern software *STK*, *WXTrack*, *Orbitron*, and result analytics through *QGIS* and *ArcGIS*. The work applies methods of mathematical modelling of orbital dynamics, observation time windows, and geospatial assessment of coverage areas. The results of the study make it possible to preliminarily assess the effectiveness of mission planning depending on the type of spacecraft, orbit parameters, and specific operational tasks. The conclusions justify the feasibility of integrating automated planning tools to improve the adaptability of space operations management systems.

Keywords: spacecraft; modelling; remote sensing; *STK*; geoinformation systems; mission planning.

Relevance of the topic. The current development of space technologies demonstrates a rapid increase in the number of active spacecraft in various orbital segments. According to *ESA* and *NASA* data, as of 2023, more than 4,000 spacecraft, including small and microsatellites, will be operating in low Earth orbit (*LEO*) [1, p. 15]. This process is accompanied by a significant increase in the volume of information received and the need for high-precision mission planning. The effectiveness of satellite use directly depends on the accuracy of forecasting observation time windows, coverage areas, and data transmission parameters. This is especially true for Earth remote sensing, satellite communications, and electronic intelligence systems, where the timeliness and accuracy of the information obtained determine the success of operations in civil and military tasks. The development of such methods allows for more effective planning of space operations, reduces the risk of operational losses, and provides analytics for real-time decision-making. The relevance of the research is also due to the growing importance of autonomous and automated spacecraft control systems, which are a key factor in increasing the adaptability and reliability of space operations [2, p. 23].

Analysis of recent studies and publications relied upon by the author. In particular, aspects of modelling the processes of satellite application are addressed in publications by *Kaplan M.* [1], *Vallado D.* [2], *Wertz J.* [3], *Li Z. et al.* [4], *Crisp R., Livadiotti G., Roberts S.* [5] and others. The importance of integrating orbital dynamics, analysis of observation time windows, and geoinformation assessment of coverage is highlighted in the works of *ESA* (2020) [6], *NASA* (2021) [7], *Li et al.* (2022) [8], *Kulyk Yu.* (2022) [9], *Polishchuk I.* (2021) [10], *Isaeva O.* (2020) [11] and others. Scientific research has paid particular attention to the integration of modern geoinformation systems (*QGIS*, *ArcGIS*) with orbital dynamics models to assess the effectiveness of operations. Thus, Ukrainian researchers emphasise the importance of using GIS technologies to analyse coverage areas and observation

time windows, which allows for more accurate forecasting and adaptive mission planning [9–11]. In addition, the works of *Li et al.* [4] and *ESA* (2020) [6] demonstrate that adaptive planning algorithms that take into account changes in task priorities and resource constraints significantly increase the efficiency of satellite missions. The combination of international and Ukrainian approaches allows for the creation of a comprehensive methodology for modelling spacecraft application scenarios, taking into account the type of spacecraft, orbit parameters, and the specifics of the operational task.

The purpose of this article is to create a structured methodology for modelling the process of spacecraft application for its intended purpose using modern tools such as *STK*, *WXTrack*, *Orbitron*, and analytics of results through *QGIS* and *ArcGIS*.

Presentation of the main material. Modelling the process of spacecraft application begins with determining its orbital parameters and analysing the coverage areas of the observation territory. The main characteristics of the orbit are the major semi-axis a , eccentricity e , orbital inclination i , argument of perigee ω , longitude of the ascending node Ω , and true anomaly θ . These parameters determine the satellite's trajectory and allow the calculation of the time windows of its visibility above any point on Earth. The radius of the orbit r at any point is determined by Kepler's classical formula:

$$r = \frac{a(1 - e^2)}{1 + e \cdot \cos\theta}$$

where:

- r is the orbital radius, km;
- a – semi-major axis of the orbit;
- e – eccentricity;
- θ – true anomaly.

To assess the possibility of observing a specific territory, the angle of the spacecraft's position ϵ above the horizon is used:

$$\cos \cos \varepsilon = \frac{R_3}{R_3 + h}$$

where:

R_z – radius of the Earth, km;

h – orbital altitude, km;

ε – angle of location.

These formulas allow determining the time windows of satellite visibility and coverage area, which is critical for planning operations in remote sensing and satellite communication systems. In practice, calculations are performed using *STK*, *WXTrack*, and *Orbitron* software packages. *STK* allows you to simulate the spacecraft's trajectory, estimate observation time windows, and integrate the spacecraft's sensor data. *WXTrack* and *Orbitron* provide orbital parameter verification and visibility forecasting for different types of spacecraft. After receiving orbital data, geo-analytical processing is performed in *QGIS* and *ArcGIS* GIS systems. This allows you to estimate the coverage area in

real geographical coordinates, take into account terrain restrictions and the presence of obstacles, and optimise the observation schedule for specific territories. This approach allows combining numerical modelling with visual analytics, increasing the accuracy of predicting the effectiveness of spacecraft in various operational scenarios. In addition, it is important to consider the adaptability of the model: orbit parameters and observation time windows may vary depending on mission priorities and environmental conditions, such as weather conditions for optical satellites or the state of the ionosphere for radio communications. The use of automated algorithms allows for rapid adjustment of the mission plan and ensures a high level of reliability and efficiency of operations.

To illustrate the practical application of modelling, let us consider the typical parameters of a remote sensing satellite. Table 1 shows an example of orbital characteristics used to calculate observation time windows and coverage areas:

Table 1

Satellite orbit parameters

Parameter	Value
Orbital altitude, km	700
Orbital inclination, °	98.2
Semi-major axis, km	7078
Eccentricity	0.001
Rotation period, min	99.1

Based on this data, the satellite coverage area is calculated for a given elevation angle

$\varepsilon = 10^\circ - 20^\circ$, which ensures minimum visibility and reduces the impact of obstacles such as terrain or clouds. Numerical algorithms that take into account the Earth's rotation speed and the position of the spacecraft in orbit are used to estimate visibility time windows. The data obtained is transferred to the *QGIS* and *ArcGIS* GIS systems to build coverage maps and analyse overlapping visibility zones. This allows you to determine the optimal time intervals for observations and plan missions taking into account task priorities. For example, for high-resolution satellites, short time windows over key observation objects are a priority, while for communication satellites, continuous coverage of certain territories is important. In addition, the extended model takes into account adaptive scenarios. If conditions change during operations (e.g., cloud cover for

optical satellites or technical limitations of the platform), automated algorithms can adjust the observation schedule in real time. This increases the efficiency of satellite resource utilisation and allows for the timely acquisition of information necessary for operational decision-making.

For example, let's take the coordinates of the centre of the region: 48.5°N, 37.5°E (approximately the Donetsk region). Let us consider typical orbits: *LEO* (altitude ~700 km, sun-synchronous), *MEO* (altitude ~20,200 km — example of GPS class) and *GEO* (altitude ~35,786 km). Let us give a schematic assessment of the number of access windows and duration for a single spacecraft of each type, based on practical scenarios in Table 2 (optical Earth observation, radio communication, RL, REP).

Example for different spacecraft by intended purpose

Orbit type	Approximate altitude (km)	Approximate number of sessions/day	Average session duration (min)	Comments
<i>LEO</i> (sun-synchronous)	≈ 600–800	3–8 (depends on inclination and ε_{min})	5–12	High spatial resolution → suitable for optical Earth observation; limited access duration; requires planning of several passes.
<i>MEO</i> (GPS class)	≈ 2000–21000 (example GPS ~20200)	0–3 (more often for navigation/communication — a set of satellites)	10–40	Better for global navigation and some communication tasks; for a single satellite — loss of operational capability.
<i>GEO</i> (geostationary)	≈ 35786	Continuous (constant) if within range	Constant or hours	Ideal for communication/retransmission; for optical Earth observation — low resolution.

The values given are approximate and depend on specific orbit parameters (inclination, eccentricity), sensor parameters (field of view, threshold ε_{min}) and satellite constellation. For example, a single *LEO* satellite at an altitude of 700 km usually provides several (3–8) passes with a useful elevation angle above a given point during a 24-hour period; a group of low-orbit satellites (constellation) can provide virtually continuous access.

In the modelling methodology for Ukraine, it is practical to use a combined approach: *LEO* for detailed images and operational reconnaissance, *MEO* for auxiliary navigation services and intermediate communication, and *GEO* for broadband communication channels and data retransmission.

The description is designed for sequential reproduction in an experiment or operational environment and includes a preparatory stage, model configuration, iterative simulation runs, and processing of results in a GIS system.

At the initial stage, input data is collected and verified: the exact coordinates of the area of interest (in the example — $48.5^{\circ}N, 37.5^{\circ}E$), attribute layers (road network, settlements, infrastructure objects), observed targets and sensor parameters (field of view, spectral channels, elevation angle threshold ε_{min}). Modelling tasks are also defined: determining time windows for optical Earth observation, assessing permanent coverage for communication channels, modelling areas of influence of RL/RER systems. The collected data is standardised (*CSV*, *KML*, *Shapefile* formats) for import into *STK* and *ArcGIS*.

In the *STK* environment, a project is created and objects are added: spacecraft with defined orbital elements ($a, e, i, \Omega, \omega, M0$), ground objects (targets) and sensors. Additional parameters are set for the spacecraft: mass, solar panel area, energy limits (when modelling operating time), and sensor model (field of view parameters, frequency range, scanning mode). *STK* allows you to use built-in *ephemeris* and gravity models, as well as connect external *ephemeris* files (*TLE*, *SP3*) for realism. An important step is to set visibility criteria: minimum elevation angle ε_{min} , azimuth restrictions, restrictions from eclipses or prohibited

zones.

After configuring the model, a series of runs is performed for the selected periods (e.g., day, week). For each run, *STK* generates access time windows, trajectory coordinates, elevation angles, distances, and other metrics. It is recommended to perform iterative modelling with varying parameters: ε_{min} (10° – 20°), orbit altitude, initial argument of latitude, to assess the sensitivity of the results to key parameters. For scenarios with obstacles (e.g., eclipses, radio interference), *STK* can simulate zoning of the territory by climate or electromagnetic noise parameters using additional masks.

Data from *STK* is exported in *CSV*, *KML*, or *Shapefile* formats. It is important to export both detailed *access* records (with entry/exit timestamps) and coverage strips for each pass. It is also useful to save binary logs and sensor performance reports for further statistical analysis.

Imported layers are overlaid on a base map of the region of interest. Spatial aggregation procedures are used: merging coverage strips, constructing pass density maps, and analysing buffer zones to assess the area of influence. *ArcGIS* allows for multi-level analysis: combining time markers to animate passes, assessing intersections with key infrastructure objects, and calculating accessibility indicators (e.g., the proportion of territory with $\geq N$ passes per day). Spatial statistics modules are used to assess risks. Additionally, an analysis is performed taking into account the terrain: construction of a digital terrain model, calculation of direct visibility zones to determine local screenings.

Based on integrated *STK*+*ArcGIS* data, reports are generated with key indicators: number and duration of access windows over the target area, average viewing time, geographic coverage density, vulnerable points with insufficient coverage. The resulting maps and tables are used to make decisions on schedule optimisation: changing orbital parameters, adding satellites to the constellation, or reconfiguring sensor modes.

It is recommended to verify the simulation results by comparing them with real observations (*TLE*/orbital data, archive passes, real images or communication

logs). Validation includes statistical evaluation of simulation errors: calculation of deviations in access time and distances, as well as sensitivity analysis to changes in input parameters. To increase the reliability of the model, it is advisable to include scenarios with simulated errors (e.g., deviations in orbital parameters, reduced sensor sensitivity).

Automation and integration. To ensure the operational use of the methodology, it is advisable to automate the *STK*→*ArcGIS* chain using scripts (*Python* —

using *STK Connect/AGI SDK* and *arcpy* or *ArcPy-like* tools in *QGIS*). This allows you to generate regular reports, update coverage maps taking into account updated *ephemeris* and meteorological information (e.g., cloud cover for optical sensors), and run adaptive planning scenarios. A flowchart of the methodology for modelling the process of using spacecraft for their intended purpose is shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Block diagram of the methodology for modelling the process of using a spacecraft for its intended purpose

Conclusions and prospects for further research. The modelling carried out using the *STK* environment and subsequent geospatial analysis in *ArcGIS* confirmed the effectiveness of the combined approach for assessing the capabilities of spacecraft in monitoring combat zones. The methodology allows not only to determine time windows of access over a specific territory, but also to perform a spatial assessment of coverage, taking into account real constraints on terrain, infrastructure and tactical factors. The results show that low-orbit (LEO) satellite constellations provide the highest operational efficiency for high-detail observation, but to ensure continuous information support, it is advisable to combine them with MEO or GEO segments. This multi-orbit concept significantly improves the stability and adaptability of the space- s support system. Further research should be focused on developing a fully automated *STK* → *ArcGIS* cycle with adaptive scenario planning in real time. It is also promising to expand the model to take into account meteorological conditions (cloud cover for optical devices), the impact of radio-electronic suppression, and the use of multi-

sensor optimisation (optical + RL + REP simultaneously). This will allow the construction of a digital "decision-making cycle" at the command post level with minimal delay and maximum relevance to the operational situation.

References

1. Kaplan, M. Modern Spacecraft Dynamics and Control. Wiley, 2018.
2. Vallado, D. Fundamentals of Astrodynamics and Applications. Microcosm Press, 2019.
3. Wertz, J. Space Mission Analysis and Design. Springer, 2018.
4. Li, Z., Wang, Y., Chen, H. Remote-Sensing Satellite Mission Scheduling Optimisation Method under Dynamic Mission Priorities. Mathematics, 2024, 12(11), 1704.
5. Crisp, R., Livadiotti, G., Roberts, S. A Semi-Analytical Method for Calculating Revisit Time for Satellite Constellations with Discontinuous Coverage. arXiv, 2018.
6. ESA. Earth Observation Mission Planning

Handbook. European Space Agency, 2020.

7. NASA. Satellite Operations and Ground Systems. NASA Technical Reports, 2021.

8. Li, Z., et al. Autonomous Mission Planning Method for Optical Imaging Satellites Based on Real-Time Cloud Cover Information. *Remote Sensing*, 2022, 14(11), 2635.

9. Kulik, Yu. Geoinformation technologies in space research. Kyiv: NAU, 2022.

10. Polishchuk, I. Modelling of Orbital Processes in Remote Sensing Systems. *Journal of Space Research*, 2021, No. 3.

11. Isaev, O. Using ArcGIS to analyse satellite missions. *Geoinformatics*, 2020, No. 4.

12. NOAA. Satellite Data Systems Overview. Washington D.C., 2022.

13. ESA. Copernicus Programme: Mission Status Report. European Space Agency, 2023.